

Substituted Piperazines. Part I. Some 1,4-Bis-polynitrophenyl-piperazines

Satya Prakash Gupta,* S. N. Bastogi, and Miss R. K. Arora

A few 1, 4-bis-polynitrophenylpiperazines have been obtained by the condensation of reactive halogenonitrobenzenes and piperazine. Where formation of more than one product is possible, only one piperazine derivative has been isolated. Structures to these compounds have also been assigned.

The wide variety of biological properties, which many of piperazine derivatives exhibit, has stimulated interest in its chemistry. Several *NN'*-disubstituted piperazines have been found to possess interesting pharmacological properties, and have found use as antihistaminics¹, fungicides², anthelmintics³, anaesthetics⁴, and sedatives⁵ in the treatment of ascariasis⁶, leukemia⁷, filariasis⁸, etc. Some of them have been found to affect the central nervous system⁹. *NN'*-Disubstituted piperazines have shown promise as potent long-acting sympatholytic and adrenolytic agents¹⁰.

During the present investigations, a few 1,4-bis-polynitrophenylpiperazines have been synthesised by the condensation of piperazine hexahydrate and reactive halogenonitrobenzenes in presence of anhydrous sodium acetate by S_N1 or S_N2 mechanism, for testing purposes. Attempts to synthesise piperazine having polynitrophenyl substituent on only one of the nitrogen atoms have failed even though an excess of piperazine was used. Best yields of disubstituted piperazines were obtained when piperazine and reactive halogenonitrobenzene were taken in 1:3 ratio.

Of the reactive halogenonitrobenzenes investigated, 1,3-dichloro-4,6-dinitro-(I), 1, 2, 3-trichloro-4,6-dinitro-(II), 1,2,5-trichloro-4, 6-dinitro-(III), 2,5-dichloro-1-bromo-4,6-dinitro-(IV), 1-chloro-2, 5-dibromo-4,6-dinitro-(V), 1,2, 5-tribromo-4,6-dinitro-(VI), and 1,3-dichloro-4,6-dinitro-2-methylbenzenes (VII) possess two reactive halogen atoms due to presence of nitro groups in their *ortho* and *para* positions. But it is noteworthy that in all these cases only one of the halogen atoms is replaced by the piperazine group. Thus compounds (I), (II) and (VII), which are symmetrically substituted, provide 1,4-bis-3-chloro-4,6-dinitro-, 1,4-bis-2,3-dichloro-4,6-dinitro-, and 1,4-bis-3-chloro-4,6-dinitro-2-methylphenylpiperazine, respectively. Identical compounds, as found by the determination of mixed m.p., were obtained by heating piperazine hexahydrate with compounds(III) and (IV). Both of them must therefore be 1, 4-bis-2,5-dichloro-4,6-dinitrophenylpiperazine.

* Present address: Chemistry Dept., D. N. College, Meerut.

1. Sloan, *J. Pharm & Pharmacol.*, 1954, 6, 718.
2. U.S.P. 2545176/1951; *Chem. Abs.*, 1951, 46, 5387r.
3. Cavier and Gaultin, Congr. Assoc. franc. advancement sci. Tunis 1951; *Tunisimed.*, 1951, 39, 902.
4. Stephenson, *Rev. Canad. Biol.*, 1952, 11, 93.
5. Payman, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, 93, 1795; U.S.P. 2418360/1948; *Chem. Abs.*, 1948, 42, 220.
6. Folia, *Pharmacol., Japan*, 1950, 45, 153; "Chemotherapy", Proc. Symposium, Lucknow, 1958.
7. Burchenal, *Cancer*, 1951, 4, 393.
8. Sewell and Hawking, *Brit. J. Pharmacol.*, 1950, 5, 230.
9. Seale, *Canad. Med. Assoc. J.*, 1951, 65, 582.
10. Swain and Naegeli, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 76, 5001.

Similarly compounds (V) and (VI) furnish 1, 4 bis-2, 5-dibromo-4, 6-dinitrophenylpiperazine due to the labile halogen present in position 1.

EXPERIMENTAL

Method (I).—1, 4-Bis-substituted phenylpiperazines were prepared by refluxing a mixture of reactive halogenonitrobenzene (0.03*M*), piperazine hexahydrate (0.01*M*), and anhydrous sodium acetate (0.04*M*) in anhydrous ethanol for several hours. The reaction mixture was cooled and washed with water and hot ethanol several times. The crude product was crystallised from nitrobenzene.

Method (II).—A solution of piperazine hexahydrate (0.01*M*) in acetone (10 ml) was treated with a solution of sodium bicarbonate (0.2 g.) in water (5 ml) and the halogenonitrobenzene (0.03 *M*), dissolved in an adequate quantity of acetone. The mixture was heated to 60° for ½ hr., cooled, and acidified with acetic acid. The product so obtained was crystallised from nitrobenzene.

The different 1, 4-bis-polynitrophenylpiperazines, prepared by the above methods, are described in Table I. The analytical values of nitrogen and halogens tally well with the calculated values.

TABLE I

1,4-Bis-substituted phenylpiperazines.

No.	1, 4-Bis-substituted phenylpiperazines.	*M.P.	Colour.	Formula	%Nitrogen	
					Found.	Reqd.
1.	2, 4-DN-	240°d	Golden yellow	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₆	19.68	20.00
2.	2, 6-DN-	278°	Orange leaflets	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₆	19.72	20.00
3.	2, 4, 6-TN-	262°	Bright yellow	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₈	21.80	22.04
4.	2-Chloro-4, 6-DN-	269°	Golden "	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₆ Cl ₂	17.05	17.25
5.	2-Bromo-4, 6-DN-	267°d	Lemon "	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₆ Br ₂	14.01	14.58
6.	3-Chloro-4, 6-DN-	273°d	Light "	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₆ Cl ₂	17.03	17.25
7.	4-Chloro-2, 6-DN-	228°d	Golden "	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₆ Cl ₂	16.87	17.25
8.	4-Bromo-2, 6-DN-	252°d	Orange	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₆ Br ₂	14.12	14.58
9.	4, 6-DN-2-Me-	260°d	Bright yellow	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₆	18.30	18.84
10.	2, 4-DN-5-Me-	281°d	Orange "	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₆	18.62	18.84
11.	2, 6-DN-4-Me-	255°	Golden "	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₆	18.38	18.84
12.	2, 4, 6-TN-3-Me-	209°d	Light brown	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₈	20.71	20.80
13.	2, 3-Dichloro-4, 6-DN-	262°d	Lemon yellow	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₆ Cl ₄	14.67	15.05
14.	2, 6-Dichloro-4, 6-DN-	280°d	" "	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₆ Cl ₄	14.75	15.05
15.	2, 5-Dibromo-4, 6-DN-	" "	" "	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₆ Br ₂	11.04	11.41
		> 300°d				
16.	2-Chloro-4, 6-DN-5-Me-	202°d	Pale	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₆ Cl ₂	14.07	14.36
17.	4-Bromo-2, 6-DN-5-Me-	" "	Lemon-yellow	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₆ Br ₂	13.68	13.80
		> 300°d				
18.	3-Chloro-4, 6-DN-2-Me-	284°	Dull yellow	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₆ Cl ₂	13.92	14.36

N.B.—DN=dinitro; TN= trinitro and Me=methyl.

*All melting points are uncorrected; 'd' denotes decomposition.

The authors' thanks are due to Dr. P. L. Bhatia, Reader in Chemistry, Regional Engineering College, Srinagar, for his keen interest during the progress of the work and to the University Grants Commission for a contingency grant to one of them (S.P.G.).

SCHOOL OF CHEMISTRY,
MEERUT COLLEGE, MEERUT
AND
DEPT. OF CHEMISTRY,
D. N. COLLEGE, MEERUT.

Received May 28, 1965.